

From Knowledge to Performance: The Role of Innovativeness in the Moroccan Hospitality Sector

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Abstract

Background: Morocco's tourism sector is crucial to the nation's economy, but it is being influenced by technological transformation, evolving consumer behaviour, and the need for innovation. As tourism continues to move towards digitalisation and personalisation, knowledge management (KM) is necessary to enhance service quality, efficiency, and competitiveness.

Objectives: This research examines the effect of Knowledge Management (KM) on firm performance in the hospitality sector in Morocco. The study also examined the mediating role of innovativeness.

Methodology: A structured questionnaire was administered to a sample of 220 respondents across Moroccan hospitality firms. The collected data were analysed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) via SmartPLS. The analysis specifically tested the direct relationship between Knowledge Management and firm performance, the relationship between knowledge management and innovativeness, and the mediating effect of innovativeness on the link between knowledge management and performance.

Results: There is a significant positive impact of knowledge management on both firm performance and innovativeness. Knowledge management also significantly leads to firm performance, indicating further the relevance of innovativeness as a competitive differentiator. However, from a mediating perspective, innovativeness does not have any significant influence on the relationship between knowledge management and firm performance, which may be explained by other organisational factors such as digital infrastructure and corporate culture.

Conclusion: The study has emphasised the integration of knowledge management and innovation strategies for business performance. Growth in Moroccan hospitality firms could be sustained by effectively leveraging knowledge resources while fostering an innovation-friendly environment.

Unique Contribution: The study extends the understanding of knowledge management and innovation in the Moroccan hospitality sector by providing empirical evidence on their impact on firms' performance in a less explored emerging market.

Key Recommendations: To improve knowledge management and innovativeness capabilities, establishments should invest in digital tools, employee training, and enhancing organisational culture. Policymakers should support sector-wide digital transformation initiatives to enhance the competitiveness of the hospitality industry.

Keywords: Knowledge Management, Innovativeness, Firm Performance, Hospitality Industry, Morocco.

Introduction

In the contemporary, globalised, and fiercely competitive marketplace, the hospitality industry is among the major stimulators of economic development, making a particular contribution to emerging markets. In Morocco, with its rich cultural heritage, historical background, and diverse tourism products, the hospitality industry is one of the leading contributors to the national GDP and a significant source of employment (World Travel & Tourism Council, 2024). However, the entire sector is exposed to growing turbulence due to factors such as rapid technological changes, evolving customer expectations, increasing demand for sustainability, and innovation.

These dynamics consequently underscore the need to leverage intangible assets, knowledge, and creativity to achieve greater organisational performance. Knowledge management has evolved as a crucial strategic resource for organisations functioning within knowledge-intensive contexts. By successfully recording, sharing, and exploiting organisational information, organisations may improve decision-making, simplify processes, and enhance customer experiences (Alavi & Leidner, 2001). In the context of Morocco's hotel industry, KM becomes especially important given the increasing use of digital technologies, such as online booking platforms, customer relationship management systems, and data analytics (Law et al., 2013). Despite these improvements, most companies in the sector fail to utilise the potential of KM practices due to a lack of resources, limited competence, and inability to align innovation in business strategy (Chen et al., 2018).

Meanwhile, innovativeness is considered the catalyst for firms to accept and implement new ideas, products, and processes, which has emerged as one of the critical factors leading to a competitive advantage. For Moroccan hospitality firms, innovativeness is essential not only to differentiate their offerings but also to address pressing challenges such as seasonality, market saturation, and the impacts of global events like the COVID-19 pandemic (Urban & van der Putten, 2023). The ability to convert knowledge into innovative outcomes can enable

institutions to deliver unique customer experiences, improve operational efficiency, and achieve sustainable growth.

While existing literature consistently emphasises the importance of knowledge management (KM) and innovativeness for enhancing firm performance, few studies have explored their interrelationship within the African hospitality context, and even fewer within Morocco's emerging market. Particularly, how innovativeness mediates the relationship between KM and firm performance remains an underexplored domain, despite the unique challenges faced by firms in emerging economies—such as resource scarcity, institutional pressures, and fluctuating market conditions—which may alter these dynamics compared to developed markets (Nieves et al., 2015).

In response to these gaps, the primary aim of this study is to critically examine the relationship between knowledge management, innovativeness, and firm performance in Morocco's hospitality sector. Specifically, it seeks to answer two core research questions:

1. What is the relationship between knowledge management, innovativeness, and firm performance in Morocco's hospitality sector?
2. To what extent does innovativeness mediate the relationship between knowledge management and firm performance?

By addressing these questions, the study contributes original insights into the mechanisms through which KM drives performance outcomes in an emerging, resource-constrained setting. It highlights innovativeness not simply as an outcome, but as a critical intermediary that can amplify the benefits of KM initiatives.

Moreover, the study holds practical significance. It offers evidence-based recommendations for hospitality practitioners and policymakers on how to leverage KM systems and innovation strategies to foster sustainable competitive advantage. In particular, the findings are expected to inform interventions aimed at fostering innovation-driven growth, enhancing operational efficiency, and improving the customer experience in Morocco's evolving tourism industry.

Finally, this research enriches the broader academic discourse by extending KM and innovation theories into an under-researched context. It contributes to the theoretical and empirical understanding of how intangible assets operate within emerging economies, combining traditional cultural offerings with modern tourism demands in a dynamic global environment.

Conceptual framework

Knowledge Management as a Driver of Innovativeness

Knowledge management is a critical enabler of innovation, underpinning the processes through which organisations develop and sustain competitive advantage. The theoretical foundations of innovation highlight the importance of knowledge as a core component. For instance, the evolutionary model of innovation emphasises the dynamic and cumulative nature of knowledge, where the ability to manage, integrate, and apply knowledge determines a firm's innovative capacity. In this context, knowledge management serves as a vital mechanism for converting organisational knowledge into value through the creation of new or improved products, services, and processes (Kalotra, 2014).

External knowledge networks play a pivotal role in enhancing organisational innovativeness. Firms that engage in interactional and systemic knowledge-sharing activities are better

positioned to leverage external resources and foster innovation (Ozkan-Canbolat & Beraha, 2019). These networks facilitate the exchange of ideas, expertise, and practices across organisational boundaries, thereby strengthening innovation capabilities. For example, in transitional economies such as China, the strategic use of external knowledge has been shown to significantly enhance the relationship between innovativeness and firm performance, highlighting the importance of adaptive knowledge strategies in dynamic environments (Liu & Wang, 2022).

Internal information management is, at its core, determined by an organisation's workforce. Staff act as channels for information delivery, a function that aids productivity and innovation (Prezenza et al., 2019). Despite this, its effectiveness in terms of information delivery is contingent on several factors, including the source's willingness to pass on information, the recipient's willingness and capability to assimilate and digest such information, and motivation towards learning (Li et al., 2019). All such interactions point towards creating a supportive inner environment within an organisation that fosters a positive information-sharing attitude and encourages continuous learning.

Knowledge spillovers, with information dissemination extending past organisational borders, form a key part of information management in companies. Inflows of such spillovers enrich a firm's innovation capabilities through access to information sources outside an organisation. (Aldieri et al., 2020) illustrate that deliberate use of spillovers raises productivity and innovation appreciably, and in the long run, generates larger economy-related payoffs through information management efficiency.

Knowledge Management in the Hospitality Sector

In knowledge management (KM), a research-based view (RBV) suggests that companies must conduct research and development (R&D) in order to build organisational knowledge and generate new ideas. According to its view, companies can gain competitiveness through the constant collection, dissemination, and application of information through R&D. By combining the output of research with practical knowledge management, companies can establish a platform for continuous improvement, make more informed decisions, drive innovation, and thereby become adaptable and enhance overall performance. practices in KM enable companies to build, save, store, and utilise knowledge in a quest to become efficient and make wiser strategic choices (Alavi & Leidner, 2001). In the knowledge-based view (KBV), awareness of knowledge holds the highest significance, as it is a significant source of competitiveness. The use of both explicit and tacit forms of knowledge is significant in efforts to build innovation and adaptability. In hotels, effective use of KM is pivotal in offering high-class service that companies can efficiently react to by adjusting to the evolving requirements of customers (Law et al., 2013). Personalisation of guests' experiences, efficient use of resources, and feedback collection following a visit can benefit immensely through proper use of KM. According to a current study, utilising computer programmes such as CRM software and data analysis can enhance effectiveness in KM (Chen et al., 2018). Nevertheless, factors such as poor company culture, lack of technology, and resistance to change can hinder companies' use of effective KM programs (Nieves et al., 2015).

Firm Performance in the Hospitality Industry

Several dimensions, including both financial and non-financial performance indicators, characterise the performance of hospitality companies. Empirical studies have demonstrated that knowledge management (KM) plays a crucial role in enhancing performance through effective decision-making and fostering a continuous improvement environment (Xie et al.,

2018). (Urban & Joubert, 2017) These organisations have demonstrated effective KM strategies and a general aptitude for innovation, displaying high adaptability in changing environments, particularly during the COVID-19 outbreak. In addition, technology implementations have further enhanced the role of KM, with ERP and AI analysis software supporting effective operations and an enriched customer experience (Chauhan & Singh, 2020).

H1: There is an important role played by knowledge management in organisational performance.

H2: Innovativeness positively impacts organisational performance.

Innovativeness as a Mediator

Innovativeness, defined in terms of an organisation's capacity for generating new processes, new goods, and new services, constitutes a key source of sustained competitive advantage in a changing environment. For a touristic organisation, such a level of innovativeness can manifest in actions such as taking up sustainable operational processes, improvements in electronic forms of communication, and developing new offerings for guests. Empirical studies have confirmed that innovativeness plays a mediator role between organisational performance and knowledge management (KM), and in the long run, aids successful innovation (Nieves & Segarra-Ciprés, 2015). High performance in terms of financial and non-financial performance, specifically in terms of profitability and customer satisfaction, is received by organisations with high innovativeness through the effective use of KM in a coordinated manner. In developing economies, adaptability and innovation are essential, as limited access to assets often necessitates unconventional problem-solving approaches (Flaminiano, 2024).

H3: Innovativeness plays a mediator role between organisational performance and knowledge management.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Methodology

Morocco, situated in North Africa and spanning 710,850 square kilometres, is renowned for its diversity in terms of vast landscapes, rich heritage, and its strategic geographical location as a bridge connecting Europe and Africa. Despite the significant impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, the hospitality industry in the country remains a key pillar of the economy, contributing substantially to the GDP and employment. Having witnessed its colossal development potential in the field, the Moroccan government, through its numerous policies and programmes, such as its Vision 2030 for tourism development, aims to develop its tourist infrastructure and grandly welcome international visitors. All these trends serve as a positive model for the hospitality sector, providing a useful guideline for studying the interrelationship

between innovation and knowledge management, specifically in terms of creating a competitive edge and mitigating the effects of economic recession.

Research Design

The present research adopts a quantitative, survey-based methodology to explore the relationship between knowledge management (KM), innovation, and performance within the Moroccan hospitality industry.

Sample and Sampling Procedure

The sample for this research comprises enterprises operating within the Moroccan hotel industry. The sample frame was generated from the membership list of the National Confederation of Tourism (CNT), which comprises hotels, guesthouses, travel agencies, and other tourism-related enterprises. An overall total of 386 answers were gathered, of which 220 were judged genuine for processing, yielding a response rate of 57 %. The final sample analysis found that over half of the respondents (48.4 %) were employed in enterprises with a workforce of 1 to 50 people, while 31.3 % reported working in organisations with 50 to 100 employees. Regarding company age, a majority (57.2 %) of respondents were linked with businesses that had been in existence for 5 to 10 years. Conversely, only a smaller share (14.7 %) worked in businesses with over 20 years of operating experience. These distributions indicate that the sample is primarily comprised of personnel from small to medium-sized enterprises with relatively moderate operational maturity, providing a unique backdrop for examining the dynamics of knowledge management and innovativeness in such organisational situations.

Measures Instrument

The research utilised a five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly agree to 5 = strongly disagree) to evaluate feedback across three key variables. The instrument was divided into three sections, each corresponding to the study's assumptions. The first portion focused on knowledge management (KM) as the independent variable, analysing both tacit and codified knowledge and its contributions to enhanced customer service (Cohen & Olsen, 2015). Elements considered included staff retention, gathering sector-specific information, and transferring expertise to stakeholders (Gold et al., 2001). The second component examined innovativeness (INN) as the mediating variable, indicating the firm's openness to innovation. This was assessed through metrics such as the launch of new goods, services, and processes, coupled with the share of revenues resulting from these innovations during the last three years (Nieves et al., 2015). The last section measured performance (PERF) as a dependent variable, integrating financial and non-financial indicators. The most important criteria included growth in sales, occupancy levels, customer complaints, repeat business, and profitability. Performance figures were collected for three years to control for seasonal and cyclical variations (Nieves et al., 2015). Mean scores of all items were summed up to portray each construct, ensuring comprehensive and reliable measurement.

Data analysis

The gathered data were analysed using SPSS 29 and SmartPLS 4 for structural equation modelling (SEM). Descriptive statistics were produced to characterise the data, while reliability and validity were assessed using Cronbach's alpha and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). A two-stage structural equation modelling technique was applied to investigate both direct and indirect effects and to verify the suggested hypothesis.

Validity and Reliability Testing

To examine construct validity, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure was applied to validate the sample sufficiency for factor analysis. The KMO values varied from 0.831 to 0.898, surpassing the tolerable threshold of 0.6, and Bartlett's test of sphericity was significant ($P < 0.001$), validating the factorisation of the variables. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was

undertaken using the primary axis factoring technique with Harris-Kaiser Case II rotation, retaining factors with eigenvalues greater than 1. Factor loadings varied from 0.71 to 0.93. For reliability testing, Cronbach’s alpha was calculated for each factor, yielding satisfactory results (>0.70).

Results

Descriptive statistics and correlation

The descriptive statistics and correlations reveal significant relationships among the study variables. Knowledge Management (KM) showed a moderate mean of 3.33 (SD = 1.2), suggesting an average level of implementation of KM practices among Moroccan hospitality firms. Innovativeness exhibited a slightly higher mean of 3.56 (SD = 1.117), indicating a stronger emphasis on innovation. Meanwhile, firm performance was moderate, with a mean of 3.17 (SD = 1.172), reflecting the varying success of hospitality firms in achieving competitive outcomes.

The correlation analysis highlighted a significant positive relationship between KM and Innovativeness ($r = 0.565$), demonstrating that firms with robust KM practices are more likely to foster innovative initiatives. Similarly, KM was moderately correlated with Performance ($r = 0.487$), suggesting that effective KM contributes to better organisational outcomes. Innovativeness showed the strongest correlation with Performance ($r = 0.634$), emphasising its critical role in driving firm success.

Table 1 : Correlation matrix and descriptive statistics

Constructs	Mean	Std. Dev.	KM	Innovativene ss	Performanc e
1. KM	3,33	1,2	1		
2. Innovativeness	3,56	1,117	0,565	1	
3. Performance	3,17	1,172	0,487	0,634	1

Reliability and validity testing

The Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) validated the reliability and validity of the constructs. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) values exceeded the threshold of 0.8, with KMO at 0.808, Innovativeness at 0.825, and Performance at 0.824, indicating adequate sampling. Bartlett’s test was significant ($p < 0.000$), supporting the factorability of the data. The percentage of variance explained by each construct was strong, with Performance explaining the highest at 84.69%, Innovativeness at 68.76%, and KM at 60.34%. Reliability metrics, including Cronbach’s Alpha (≥ 0.738), Composite Reliability (CR ≥ 0.752), and Average Variance Extracted (AVE ≥ 0.616), were satisfactory, demonstrating internal consistency and convergent validity.

Table 2: CFA results and reliability scores

Construct	KMO and Bartlett’s Test	Percentage Varia nce Explained	Cronbac h’s Alpha	CR	AVE
KM	0.808 (P <	60,34%	0,738	0.752	0,672

	0.000)				
INN	0.825 (P < 0.000)	68,76%	0,772	0.823	0,635
PERF	0.824 (P < 0.000)	84,69%	0,835	0.849	0,616

Intercorrelation of Variables

The intercorrelation analysis demonstrated strong relationships among the study constructs, supporting their validity. The diagonal values (square roots of the AVE) for Knowledge Management (KM = 0.786), Innovativeness (INN = 0.828), and Performance (PERF = 0.750) exceeded their respective intercorrelation coefficients with other constructs. This confirms discriminant validity, as each construct is strongly related to its own measures than to others. KM showed a moderate positive relationship with Innovativeness (r = 0.479) and Performance (r = 0.464), emphasising its importance in fostering innovation and driving firm success. Innovativeness exhibited a stronger relationship with Performance (r = 0.595), highlighting its critical role as a driver of organisational outcomes.

Table 3 : intercorrelation of the constructs

Variables	KM	INN	PERF
KM	0.786		
INN	0.479	0.828	
PERF	0.464	0.595	0.750

Hypothetical Model

Hypotheses testing results were largely supportive of the proposed relationships. H1, which posits that KM positively influences Performance, was supported ($\beta = 0.319$, $t = 4.132$, $p < 0.000$). Similarly, H2, hypothesising that KM positively affects Innovativeness, was also supported ($\beta = 0.216$, $t = 3.468$, $p = 0.001$). Innovativeness was found to significantly predict Performance (H3: $\beta = 0.219$, $t = 3.788$, $p < 0.000$). However, H4, which tested the role of innovativeness in mediating the KM-Performance connection, was not supported ($\beta = 0.108$, $t = 1.471$, $p = 0.141$), suggesting that the indirect effect may not be statistically significant.

Table 4 : Hypothesis test

Hypothesis	Mean	Std. Dev.	t-Statistic	p-value	Status
KM -> PERF	0.319	0.078	4.132	0.000	Supported
KM -> INNOV	0.216	0.062	3.468	0.001	Supported
INN -> PERF	0.219	0.058	3.788	0.000	Supported
KM -> INN -> PERF	0.108	0.071	1.471	0.141	Not supported

Discussion

This research affirms the fragile nexus between performance, innovativeness, and knowledge management (KM) in Moroccan hospitality organisations. Findings validate earlier studies by

emphasising the crucial role of KM in building organisational shock-resistance, particularly during global crises. Specifically, the results indicate that Moroccan hospitality firms with robust KM practices were better equipped to maintain service continuity, quickly adapt operational procedures, and retain customer loyalty even under adverse conditions. In practical terms, organisations with effective KM showed significant improvements in customer satisfaction, innovation capabilities, and operational efficiency, echoing general studies on the strategic leverage of KM in resource-constrained environments (Urban & Joubert, 2017).

The study further highlights the contribution of innovativeness as an intermediate factor, even when its direct influence appears limited. The evidence supports the notion that innovativeness plays a vital role in transforming knowledge into actionable ideas and solutions. This finding aligns with Chen et al. (2018), who emphasise innovativeness as a key to achieving competitive differentiation and adaptability in uncertain contexts. Moreover, the partial mediation of innovativeness suggests that while creativity and idea generation are essential, their effectiveness heavily depends on supporting factors such as technological readiness, leadership vision, and internal collaboration mechanisms. This broader view is consistent with Xie et al. (2018), who underscore the significance of social structures and digital technologies in enhancing KM effectiveness.

The study also exposes critical structural challenges faced by Moroccan organisations, particularly in terms of limited resources and underutilisation of technology. These barriers closely mirror those experienced in other developing countries, such as Lesotho (Urban & Matela, 2022). Overcoming such constraints demands targeted investment in capacity development, digital infrastructure, and a broader organisational culture shift towards innovation. The findings reinforce the idea that government intervention is vital, not only in providing infrastructure but also in creating policy frameworks that incentivise innovation and KM adoption. Success stories from other developing economies further illustrate that coordinated multi-level support is essential to unlock the full potential of KM for sustainable competitiveness.

Conclusion

This study advances knowledge management (KM) and innovation theory within Morocco's hospitality sector. It applies established KM models to industry-specific challenges and tests the Knowledge-Based View (KBV) and Resource-Based View (RBV), both of which highlight knowledge and innovation as drivers of competitiveness and organisational sustainability. Findings show that effective KM improves service quality, internal efficiency, and overall performance, supporting strategic advantage in volatile markets.

Managerially, the study underscores the need for a culture of knowledge sharing and continuous learning, supported by investments in KM systems, staff training, and leadership development. Structured policies for capturing explicit and tacit knowledge are essential for embedding best practices and achieving sustainable success.

Practically, the study recommends that businesses adopt digital collaboration tools, conduct regular knowledge audits, and systematically measure KM performance. Given the context-specific nature of the findings, future research should pursue cross-cultural and longitudinal studies to better understand KM dynamics across diverse hospitality environments.

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